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**Pensions Programmed Withdrawal and Insurance Life Annuity In Nigeria.
A Comparative Analysis as Options to Nigerian Retirees**

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ABSTRACT

This study is a comparative study that analysed the pension programmed withdrawal and insurance life annuity as regards to retiree options at the point of retirement. This is sequel to the fact that Nigeria retirees have undergone many challenges of pensions payment. The study used content analysis research design and the following variables: guaranteed period; return on the investment; security of the fund and benefit payment. The analysis revealed that retirees are interested in programmed withdrawal more than annuity because of better edge and more trust associated with programmed withdrawal, including risk of losing their fund upon death at annuity option. It was recommended that the commission needs a provisional guideline that will enable pensions administrators to recalculate retirees monthly payment periodically to reflect the significant of the investment return. However, creating an enabling environment to expand safe investment of retiree fund across the border.

Keywords: guaranteed period; return on the investment; security of the fund and benefit payment; programmed withdrawal and insurance life annuity

1. INTRODUCTION

The global shift towards the defined contributory pensions from defined benefit pensions has many positive aspects both for employees and for employers. Among them, is labour market mobility because of decrease in accrual risk; reallocates investment risk from the corporate sector to the household sector, which has potential implications for financial stability. In defined contributory pensions, employees bear investment and longevity risks, exposed employee to market timing risk at the point of retirement. (Broadbent J et al, 2006)

Accordingly, section 7 (1) of the Pensions Reform Act 2014 as amended allows withdrawal of lump sum from the total amount credited to his retirement saving account provided that the amount left after the lump sum withdrawal shall be sufficient to procure programmed withdrawal or annuity for life from a life insurance company licensed by the National Insurance Commission (NAICOM) with monthly or quarterly payment.

An annuity is an investment made through an insurance company. It represents a contractual relationship between an annuitant and the company.

According to Williamson (1993), states that annuities are offered only by the insurance industry, they do not have anything to do with life insurance or any other type of insurance coverage. Annuities are marketed and sold through brokerages firms, insurance agencies banks, saving and loan institutions, financial planners and investment advisors

When purchase or invest in an annuity, the insurance company gives certain assurances. The guarantees depend upon the type of annuity. There are two different types of annuities fixed (a set rate of return) and variables (the investor choose from a series of portfolio that range from conservative to aggressive) In Nigeria, the contributory pensions scheme seeks among others that every workers receives his retirement benefits as and when due.

Under programmed withdrawal, administered by pension fund administrator, the retiree get his pension on a monthly or quarterly basis by calculating how he wants it to be paid by his pensions fund administrator based on his expected life span. It will cease to get any further payment once the stated years (lifespan) has elapsed (Joe, 2010). On the other hand, annuity is paid on a monthly or quarterly basis by the insurers to the pensioner, until the retiree dies.

As provided for by the Act, the modalities for payment of retirement benefits are life annuity, which is obtainable from life insurance companies or through programmed withdrawal which is obtainable from pension fund administrators. Either of the two methods is available depending on the choice of the retiree.

Objective of the study

The main objective of this study is to analyse the comparative between pension programme withdrawal and insurance life annuity as regards to retiree options at the point of retirement.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 presents an in-depth literature review on annuities. It discusses income from annuities, investment from annuities, procedure for accessing life annuity including prior research on annuity and programmed withdrawal. Section 3 discusses data methodology and the research design. A discussion with the variables. Conclusions and Recommendations" are presented in Section 4 and 5.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This is a product offered by a pension fund administrators for periodic payment to a beneficiary of a retirement savings account as specified in section 4 of the Pensions Reform Act 2004. It is calculated based on determined formula and methodology. The pensions fund administrator shall determine the amount of periodic withdrawals to make from the retiree retirement savings account in line with the regulations on the computations of programmed withdrawals issued by the commission.

The pension fund administrator notify the commission by sending information relating to the retiree and shall request the commission"s approval of programmed withdrawal arrangements. The commission would within five working days of receipt of the notification communicate its approval or rejection to the pensions fund administrator and shall transfer the retiree"s retirement saving account to the retirees" database.

Where the retiree opts for lump sum withdrawal as approved by the commissions, the pensions fund administrator shall issue a payment instruction to its pensions fund custodian to effect the payment. The payment shall be made to the retiree designated bank account.

Williamson (1993) states that annuity is an investment made through an insurance company. It represents a contractual relationship between the insurer (insurance company) and the annuitant (annuity purchaser). The insurance company gives certain assurances. The guarantees depend upon the type of annuity.

Annuity is a series of payments made at (equal) intervals in consideration of a lump sum, or a regular contribution made over a pre-defined period with the expectation of receiving an agreed regular payment for life at expiration of the period. (Business day 2014)

We have different types of annuity but the type being made popular in Nigeria through the Pensions Reform Act 2004 is called *Immediate Annuity*.

Haruna, (2014) defined immediate annuity as an insurance product that is purchased by retirees using the balance standing to the credit of the Retirement Saving Account as premium in consideration of an immediate monthly payment for life by the insurance company.

Immediate annuities are annuities that start immediately, payments can be sent monthly, quarterly or annually. The receiving amount will be specific depending on the total annuity investment. Immediate annuities vary on the payment from one insurance company to the other. Once an insurance company gives a specific quote, the difference is the rate of return that each company is willing to offer. The longer the period chosen, the lesser income received per month, quarter or year. Thus, someone who has N6,000,000 and wants an immediate annuity structured for monthly payments of a 10-year period will get larger monthly payments than someone who has the same amount of money to invest but is looking for monthly income for life (assuming his life expectancy is greater than 10 years).

In other words, deferred annuity is a type of annuity that provides with the flexibility of growth for a short or long period of time, or later. If the annuitants choose, they can receive income from annuity either through sporadic or scheduled withdrawals. (Williamson 1993)

The owner of a deferred annuity can request that a certain amount of income be sent to him annually and the rest be reinvested. Or, as in most cases, the owner of the annuity simply has the principal and any earned interest and, or growth reinvested automatically.

It is an annuity that provides money to grow, owners may or may never need an income stream. The deferral process can offer a great deal of flexibility. Besides automatic reinvestment, the contract owner also has the ability, subject to possible cost, to terminate the investment or simply withdraw part of the principal.

A fixed rate annuity provides the contract owner with a guaranteed rate of return. The rate of return varies from insurance companies to another including with different maturities. The most common maturities for annuities are one, three or five years.

The rate of return is usually locked in for a specific period of time. The rate of return is guaranteed for the contracted period. The rate of return will be received whether or not the stock market goes up, interest rates go down, or the insurance company has a profitable or losing year.

The longer the commitment, the higher the interest rate, the interest credited can either be sent annually or reinvested, so the larger amount earns higher interest. It is most popular with people who want assurances about the safety of their principal. They can provide a great stabilizing force for moderate or aggressive investors who need some balance in their overall portfolio.

Variable annuity is a type of annuity that the insurance company does not share in any profits with the annuitant, and it will not absorb any losses of the annuitant. The annuitants are limited by the investment choices offered by the insurance company.

The investor who realizes that gains and losses may occur but wants investment flexibility to more monies among a family of funds will be attracted to a variable annuity.

The procedure for accessing life annuity is when a retiree chooses a Life Annuity. The retiree shall base on his retirement saving account obtain quotes for life annuity from the list of approved insurance companies by National Insurance Commission. The retiree shall obtain a provisional agreement from his chosen insurance and submit same to his pension administrator.

The pension administrator within 7 days from receipt of application from the retiree seek approval from PENCOM to transfer the agreed premium to the insurer. The pension administrator shall instruct the pension custodian to issue cheque for the premium approved in favour of the insurance company within 7 working days of receipt of approval from PENCOM.

Empirical Review

Broadbent et al (2006) states that UK, Australia, Nigeria and Canada pension balances are locked in until retirement age. In UK and Canada, early withdrawals are not permitted, while purchase of an annuity is compulsory at the age of 69 and 75 respectively. In Nigeria, pensions assess are at age 50, while early withdrawal are only permitted in exceptional circumstances. Investment in a „locked-in“ retirement saving account where annual withdrawal limits are pre-specified is also permitted in Canada. Australian employees in defined contributory plans have the choice of purchasing an annuity or taking the entire balance as lump sum withdrawal as early as age 55.

Olona,(2014)is of the view that life annuity take care of the basic fear of an intending retiree which is of the risk of out living his income (longevity risk). He also mention the investment risk borne by the annuity provider over the programmed withdrawal as a guaranteed sum is given to the annuitant on a regular basis in spite of harsh investment climate that might be experienced by the insurance company. He affirmed that both the pension administrators and annuity providers are partners in progress as there cannot be an effective administration of annuity without involvement of pension’s administrators who are supposed to accumulate the fund to use in purchasing the annuity for life.

Yermo (2001) reports that the demand for individual (or joint) life annuities has been limited to date, only few OECD counties with exception. He is of the view that annuities markets either do not yet exist or are still in an incipient stage of development.

Mitchell and McCarthy (2002) investigated the main exception in the UK where compulsory annuitization of defined contributory plans and personal pension’s plans has supported the development of the market. He reported that US has a well-developed variable annuities market but variable annuities are used mainly as an asset accumulation vehicle.

Okpor, (2010)states that pension administrator has the advantage over annuity providers because they are the ones who have been keeping the retirement saving account for the workers when they were still working. They know those who are going to retire soon and when they are retiring, they make them to convert their retirement saving account to programme withdrawal.

Brown and Warshawsky (2000) find out that only 30 percent of US defined contributory plans offer annuities as an option on retirement. They reported that most countries, the choice of whether to annuitize defined contributory plan balances is left up to individual and in practice few choose to do so.

Broadbent et al (2006) in reviewing the empirical and theoretical results on the value of low annuities demand are influence by factors: a need to set aside assets to meet unexpected large expenditure, irreversibility of annuitization decisions, self-insurance within families, the attractiveness of competing investment, market imperfections and institutional and regulatory barriers to the provision of annuities.

Onons, (2013) in Daily Independent compared the programmed withdrawal and life annuity using AIICO

Pensions Managers. The result was that majority of pensions contributors might have been opting for programmed withdrawal instead of life annuity when they want to retire because they are convinced that they can continue to trust the pension administrator. He indicated that out of the company's contributors that have now retired, only about 30% opted for life annuity while about 70% retirees chose programmed withdrawal.

Poterba (2001) cites research showing decline in the value of annuities over time in UK and US market where it is compulsory, as a fraction of the premium, there has been a decline in the ratio of the typical monthly pay-out, which in turn is related in part to the decline in long term interest rates. The mortality rate may pose a factor for an insurer that guesses wrong and finds that people are living longer than it expected may face a significant unplanned liability. Friedberg and Webb (2006) reported on the estimate that the medical breakthrough that eradicated cancer, diabetes and circulatory disease would increase the present value on payment on joint life and survivor annuities by roughly half. They find out that life insurers face little ability to hedge against this risk, because no reinsurance mechanisms for addressing the aggregate mortality risk.

3. Research Design and method of Analyses

Our research design is content analysis. It is a method where the content of the message forms the basis for drawing inferences and conclusions about the content (Nachmias and Nachmias, 1976). Our strategy is based on interface of observation and document analysis.

Content analysis is also defined as a method of observation in the sense that instead of asking people to respond to questions, it "takes the communications that people have produced and asks questions of communications" (Kerlinger, 1973).

However, our comparative analyses are based on the pensions programmed withdrawal and insurance life annuity in as regards to retirees' option in Nigeria. Interferences were drawn from the Pensions Reform Act 2014 as amended including the practices of license Pension Fund Administrators and Insurances organizations. Variables analysis are as follows: guaranteed period; return on the investment; security of the fund and benefit payment.

Investment of all funds relating to retiree life annuity shall be recorded in a separate and distinct account from other funds managed by the insurance company. The fund is in the annuity pool with insurance company, which return on investment belongs to the pool.

Insurance companies are mandated to invest retiree life annuity fund in line with approved investment limits prescribed by Pensions Commission and Insurance Commission. The following maximum portfolio limits in these assets classes apply

S/No	Investment Instrument	Maximum Limit %
1	Real Estate	35%
2	Equity (Quoted)	20%
3	Money Market Instrument	50%
4	Corporate Debts	25%
5	Government Securities	100%
6	Other	5%

The retiree fund is strictly for employees of all sectors who were previously registered members of the retirement saving account fund but who have now retired from active service and have chosen the

programmed withdrawal retirement option. Positive or negative return on investment belongs to the retiree in his retirement saving account.

The fund is operated using the concept of unitisation exactly like that of the retirement saving account and has its own unit price. Administration are mandated to invest retiree funds in line with the approved investment limits prescribed by the commission.

Although the regulations on investment of pension fund assets apply in respect of authorised markets for trading quality of instrument or securities, performance benchmarks, per issue or per issuer limits etc.

In addition, the retiree fund is wholly invested in fixed income securities. The following maximum portfolio limits in these assets classes apply;

S/No	Investment Instrument	Maximum Limit %
1	Government Securities	100%
2	Money Market Instrument	60%
3	Corporate Debts Instrument	40%

Brown et al (2008) argue that investment framing of annuities may be an important factor in the low popularity of annuities. They reported that presenting annuities in a consumption frame (as a product that will yield per month in income) results in significantly higher take up than presenting annuities in an investment frame (as an investment that will yield a return per month).

It was indicated that investment on annuity fund are exposed to both fixed and variable securities, which makes the fund more aggressive than retiree fund. Though the fund belongs to the insurance company pool. The annuitant does not benefit from positive or negative return on investment as the annuity payment is fixed.

The investment on programmed withdrawal which is on retiree fund is completely equities free which makes the fund less aggressive or risk free, while an appreciation in value is desirable. Return on investment belongs to the retiree as well as the retiree bears the loss in case of negative return.

4. CONCLUSION

This study examines the pensions programmed withdrawal and insurance life annuity in Nigeria. A comparative analysis that analysed the retiree programmed withdrawal and insurance life annuity. The following variables were analysed: guaranteed period: return on the investment: security of the fund and benefit payment. The result shows that, though life annuity pays for life, the pensions programmed withdrawal has yielded a very impressive return that can still take care of the retirees throughout their life. Secondly, that the investment return on annuity fund belongs to the insurance company while the investment return on programmed withdrawal fund belongs to the retiree, making programmed withdrawal better option for many retirees. Thirdly, that annuity fund are held by the insurance companies while programmed withdrawal funds are held by Pensions Custodians, putting programmed withdrawal funds more secured than annuity funds. Fourthly, life annuity benefits the annuitants" while programmed withdrawal benefits the retirees as well as the next of kin, because the outstanding account balance will be paid to the beneficiary upon retiree death. Finally, programmed withdrawal fund can be transfer to annuity fund as well as having the same uniform agreement form from the pension"s commission while annuity fund cannot be transfers back to programmed withdrawal. However, annuity agreements defers from insurance companies to another.

It was concluded that because of the better edge that programmed withdrawal has, retiree opt for programmed withdrawal more than annuity. This result was in agreement with Yermo 2001 ; Okpor, 2010 ; Broadbent et al 2006 ; Onons, 2013 ; Poterba 2001; Friedberg and Webb 2006; Brown 2007 who mentions the barriers of annuity as follows: retirees trust to pensions administrators over the years; a need to set aside assets to meet unexpected large expenditure; irreversibility of annuitization decisions; self-insurance within families; the attractiveness of competing investment; market imperfections; decline in long term interest rates; no reinsurance mechanisms for addressing the aggregate mortality risk; as a gamble that depends on whether or not involve retirees will live long enough to make the annuity worthwhile

5. RECOMMENDATION

This paper recommends that since the programmed withdrawal has made reasonable return for retiree over the years while paying same monthly payment, the commission needs a provision guideline that will enable pensions administrators to recalculate retirees monthly payment periodically, which will reflect the significant of the investment return when the retiree is still alive. The insurance commission and pensions commission needs to continue to work on the synergy in respect to the security, investment guideline and benefit payment of retirement fund to guarantee the safety of the fund. Finally, the commissions need to provide conducive environment to expand investment of retirees fund to secure safe investments across the border to benefit more return.

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